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The LUNZ Hub's RESPECT Project

The interdisciplinary Rapid Engagement with Stressed Peatland Environments and Communities in Transformation (RESPECT) project is affiliated with the Land Use for Net Zero, Nature and People (LUNZ) Hub and is funded by the UKRI Land Use for Net Zero programme. RESPECT aims to produce data, methods, landholder tools and proposals for governance reforms to change agricultural practices on peatland. RESPECT brings together researchers across Scotland and England with expertise in the natural and social sciences, humanities and law. RESPECT will also produce the Peatland Triage Tool (PTT), providing decision-support for landowners, land managers, farmers and crofters (collectively 'landholders') seeking to undertake peatland restoration. Upon completion, RESPECT will be able to provide a solid evidence base, and tools to inform land use decisions in relation to the restoration and sustainable management of agricultural peatlands.

This response was drafted with input from across our interdisciplinary RESPECT Team.

RESPECT response to the Scottish Government's consultation on Scotland's Climate Change Plan – 2026-2040

This document presents the RESPECT project's response to the Scottish Government's consultation on [Scotland's Climate Change Plan 2026–2040](#) (CCP). It focuses on the land use and agriculture sectors (particularly the protection, restoration and sustainable management of agricultural peatlands) which are key to meeting Scotland's statutory net-zero target. While welcoming the focus on peatlands in the CCP and the integration of just transition principles, the response argues that a just transition will not occur automatically and must be intentionally designed into climate policy and delivery. Current policies to direct (peat)land use change are fragmented, heavily reliant on voluntary action and unregulated markets, and insufficiently integrated with agricultural policy, land reform and community wealth building. A continued focus on hectare-based targets (with a new proposed target of 400,000 hectares of restored peatland by 2040) and private finance risks reinforcing existing inequalities in land governance and access to funding for small farmers, crofters, tenants and communities, without guaranteed environmental success. The response calls for a more strategic, integrated and outcome-focused approach that embeds climate action within broader environmental and social policies, ensuring that climate change action delivers fair processes, meaningful participation and just outcomes at local level.

SECTION 1: DELIVERING A JUST TRANSITION

1. What are your views on our approach to delivering a just transition for people and communities?

We welcome the integration of the statutory just transition principles throughout this Plan. Recognition of the transition towards net zero as both an environmental and a social challenge in Scotland should not be undervalued. However, a just transition must be intentionally designed into policy. It will not happen automatically, and it requires bolder action and much better integration of policies.

Therefore, and in addition to our comments on the proposed indicators (Q 29-33), we flag some more structural challenges and opportunities to delivering a just transition which should be addressed in this Plan:

- **Integrated policy to support a just transition:** Delivering a just transition to net zero is, ultimately, about managing trade-offs in a fair and just way. In the context of land use, this requires a strategic

approach to land use change to reconcile a multitude of policy objectives and economic and social demands on land, keeping in mind the restricted (physical and social) capacities of land and landholders. A clear, coherent and well-supported strategic approach to inform policymaking and

reform is currently lacking. This has practical implications and may undermine just outcomes. For example, whilst peatland restoration is central to this draft CCP, peatlands sit within a very fragmented area of law- and policymaking, as recognised by the Annexes (Annex 2, pp 132-133). A lack of integration of agricultural policy and public funding for peatlands has resulted in conflict, for example, restoration may impact on the eligibility of producers to receive some agricultural payments. Where the CCP places a lot of emphasis on the Fourth Land Use Strategy (LUS4) to deliver a more integrated approach, [our response to the proposals for LUS4](#) has called into question how capable LUS4 will be of doing so, as the draft simply copy-pastes objectives from other policies, without bringing them together to identify conflict and opportunities for synergies between aims and targets.

- **Action-oriented sectoral policy to deliver a just transition:** The CCP relies on sectoral just transition plans, including the Land Use and Agriculture Just Transition Plan (LAJTP), to deliver the CCP's commitments to a just transition to net zero. However, our [response to the draft LAJTP](#) offers critical reflections on the LAJTP's lack of integration with the LUS4 and the National Just Transition Outcomes, and the lack of concrete proposals, timelines, and responsibilities to deliver a just transition for the land use and agricultural sectors in an action-oriented manner.
- **Robust regulation of private finance and natural capital markets:** As outlined in our [response to Scottish Parliament's call for views](#) on 'Draft Climate Change Plan Scrutiny', the current approach to realising land use change – such as the restoration and sustainable management of peatlands - for climate targets, relies heavily on voluntary action by farmers and landowners, shaped by unregulated market dynamics. This is insufficient to guarantee public goods and a just transition. Policies are needed to regulate voluntary carbon and nature markets to ensure projects deliver genuine, lasting climate, ecological and social benefits and do not simply serve as a mechanism for 'moving money around' (see also Q 13). This includes establishing clear legal responsibilities and liabilities for project delivery, especially in complex collaborations which require the setting up of new companies.
- **Justice as an integral part of policy design and delivery:** At the moment, insofar communities are concerned, the just transition approach in the CCP focuses on participation (in policymaking) and community benefits (albeit primarily in the energy sector). What is lacking is scrutiny of actual proposed policies through a justice lens, particularly the reiteration of the 250,000 hectares peatland restoration target, and introduction of a new target of 400,000 hectares of restored peatland by 2040. Measuring success in hectare-based metrics [obscures social impacts on the ground](#), including the impacts of large-scale restoration under long-term agreements (e.g., minimum 30 years and average duration of 80 years of contracts under the Peatland Code) on power dynamics within current and future communities, and the distribution of benefits linked to concentrated resource ownership.

2. We recognise that workers face particular impacts from the Plan and we have outlined our approach to supporting the transition of the workforce, including skills for jobs. What skills, training and qualification provisions will be most important in a net zero future and what more could be done to support them?

The CCP and the new [Peatland ACTION Five Year Partnership Plan 2025-2030](#) regard the creation of jobs in remote and rural locations as an important positive impact of peatland restoration and for delivering a just transition to net zero. However, there are challenges in relation to green jobs and peatland restoration, as peatland restoration is currently unable to support secure, fulltime and year-round employment.

Peatland restoration is a relatively new activity compared to forestry, and it is not yet a standalone and established industry. The nature of the work means that restoration activities are seasonal, with most work taking place in winter. Projects are also temporary in nature and there is currently no reliable pipeline of ongoing work. Contractors competing to take up peatland restoration projects will likely be active in other local industries, e.g., Calmax Construction Ltd. is the largest building and civil engineering company in the Western Isles and is also involved in peatland restoration projects. These contractors are, therefore, likely to use existing employees with relevant skills (e.g., machine operators) to undertake the work, rather than create new local jobs that require re-skilling and re-training. Similarly, preparatory work such as surveying is likely to be undertaken by existing organisations (e.g., environmental NGOs) with trained staff.

A strategy is needed to explore how more secure local jobs may be created through peatland restoration initiatives, which can bring economic activity to remote areas. For example, job creation could be one of the indicators to be considered in the setting of policy-defining targets for peatland restoration beyond the current hectare-based targets (Q 32). The change will not only require training, but also the suggestion of alternative employment for workers where restoration work is seasonal, without secure or not long-term contracts, in order to draw new workers to the sector. It should, however, be kept in mind that until the sector has grown, it will be hard for new companies to compete for the projects and create new jobs.

SECTION 2: SECTORAL CONTRIBUTIONS AND POLICIES AND PROPOSALS *Agriculture and Land Use, Land Use Change and*

Forestry (LULUCF)

13. How can the Scottish Government encourage sustainable land use, that is also productive for local communities?

A just transition and community wealth building should be at the core of Scottish climate policy. We make a number of recommendations in relation to public funding, the regulation of private finance and the delivery of community value from natural resource management including through adaptive governance:

- **A shift towards [outcome-based public funding](#), including Peatland ACTION funding.** Allocating funds on the basis of clearly defined, transparent outcomes rather than hectare counts will contribute to a more effective targeting of public funds to deliver on multiple policy objectives. A shift in approach could refocus funding decisions on achieving multiple environmental and social objectives such as climate change mitigation and adaptation, biodiversity, water, community wealth building and a just transition, as well as potential benefits from and for the historic environment.
- **Robust regulation of private finance and natural capital markets:** The plan reiterates the reliance on private investment through the Natural Capital Markets Framework. Private investment can complement public funds, but its role must be carefully managed (see also Q 1). The current model, which relies on an unregulated voluntary carbon market can undermine the position of communities in natural resource use and management and it can exacerbate social inequalities by favouring large, simple projects over smaller, more complex ones. [Regulation of voluntary carbon and nature markets](#) is needed to ensure that these markets are underpinned by legislation, not just voluntary codes, aligns with public policy goals including community wealth building and land reform, require investment to deliver shared benefits for public, private, and community interests, in line with Scotland's [Principles for Responsible Investment in Natural Capital](#) and avoids the underwriting of financial risks by the public purse while profits are privatised.
- **Support for adaptive and inclusive governance mechanisms.** At the moment there is a significant focus on delivery of community benefits through benefit funds, even though [research commissioned by the Scottish Land Commission](#) shows that inclusive governance models with internal democratic structures and opportunities for integration of local voices may allow for more impactful and equitable sharing of private, public and community value from land. We welcome the commitment to continued support for Regional Land Use Partnerships (RLUPs) in this Plan, however, it is currently unclear whether lessons have been taken from the initial pilots to improve the functioning of the RLUPs, to consider stronger powers in relation to influence decision-making on land and the distribution of funding in accordance with previous [advice from the Scottish Land Commission](#) (2020) and a [report by Scottish Environment LINK](#) (2025), and to upscale the model to other regions in Scotland including those that are key for peatland management and restoration.

14. What do you think about our proposals for planting trees and restoring natural habitats like peatlands?

It is positive to see the continuous focus on peatlands in this draft CCP, and the progress in activities including a 42% increase in peatland hectares restored from 2023/24 to 2024/25 (Annex 2, p 129). However, as observed elsewhere in this consultation response, and in [our response to the Scottish Parliament's call for views to scrutinise the Climate Change Plans \(pre-consultation\)](#), the focus of the hectare-based targets on scale as a measure of success are driving restoration efforts in a way that does not only leave uncertainty about the climate and biodiversity effects of projects on the ground (Q 22-25), but obscures potential negative socioeconomic effects including those relating to the concentration of power over land in Scotland.

This is particularly important now that the new [Peatland ACTION Five Year Partnership Plan 2025-2030](#) explicitly invites “larger projects [to apply for funding] to increase scale, efficiency and value for money”.

The draft CCP commits to looking into increasing the proportion of the most highly degraded and emitting peat that is restored. Whilst this might be a more effective approach to targeting public funds for restoration, we question how this will be delivered alongside commitments to increase the area of peatland restoration by 10% each year considering the budget for peatland restoration in the [Scottish budget](#) has remained similar to 2024/2025 levels (a reduction compared to 2025/2026 levels which included a temporary financial boost).

In addition, to peatland restoration, we welcome to recognition of the importance of the protection of existing peatlands/carbon stocks in the SEA (Q 25), but this focus seems to be missing from policies relating to the sustainable management of agricultural peatlands. Lastly, what is also missing from this CCP are policies relating to peatland creation or the creation of other habitats/carbon sinks.

15. How can the Scottish Government support farming to become more climate-friendly while continuing to support food production and improve biodiversity?

The CCP recognises the need for alignment and integration of several relevant policies in the LULUCF sector including peatland restoration, due to the diverse land uses on peatlands. However, this should include agricultural policy which is essential to supporting a just transition to net zero in the agricultural sector, notably in relation to farmers and crofters who are currently using peatlands for agriculture.

The design of post-Brexit Scottish agricultural policy provides a critical opportunity to support the protection, sustainable management and restoration of agricultural peatlands. However, there is currently a lack of integration of agricultural policy with peatland and wider land use policy (Q 1), and details are lacking on how the Agriculture and Rural Communities (Scotland) Act 2024 will be implemented through new schemes. Previous versions of the Agricultural Reform Route Map were explicit on links with peatland restoration funding, but this is less obvious now. GAEC 6 on the maintenance of soil organic matter including for peatland areas is a welcome development – aligning Scotland with the EU – but research is needed to scrutinise the impact/environmental effects of this new condition on the ground. In addition, it must be noted that where, overall, there is significant uncertainty about the direction/content of the Scottish agricultural policy and the timeframes in which new conditions and schemes will be rolled out, farmers and crofters may be more likely to turn to private finance, thereby limiting the reach/influence of policy on peatland management. Clear policies and secure payments need to be a priority to allow public funding to remain the primary mechanism to secure public environmental goods such as climate change mitigation from agricultural land. In relation to both peatland-related private finance opportunities and public grants we also note the access barriers that are faced by many agricultural land users, including crofters and grazing committees, tenant farmers and small-scale producers, which requires support to increase capacity of these groups and overcome transaction costs to allow for engagement with complex funding schemes.

The Plan needs to be more explicit on the specific needs of and opportunities for agricultural peatlands. In particular, we see an opportunity for this Plan to include proposals and policies to action the above under Outcome 5 for the agriculture sector, which reads: ‘Carbon sequestration on agricultural land is increased, and carbon stores are maintained or increased’. More research is required to understand how multifunctional peat landscapes can be created to move beyond the ‘sheep versus peat’ divide and to also consider other (agricultural) land uses. Whilst many environmental goods can be derived from agricultural areas, the delivery of these goods is often inextricably linked to a farmers' primary function and identity as food producers (see this [policy briefing by Proctor *et al.*](#), University of Newcastle), which should be recognised by policy reforms. Lastly, native livestock could deliver multiple benefits from land, but to overcome economic barriers to the (re)introduction of native breeds adequate public support is required (e.g., through a new High Nature Value Agriculture scheme) which also needs to be integrated with peatland policy.

Lastly, capacity building and skills development is required to support changes in agricultural practices and ensure that no one is left behind in the transition. Models of delivery could be farmer-led (e.g., on-farm demonstration, training events, farmer-led networks, peer to peer learning) or led by land advisory professional bodies through CPD, training, etc. Co-design is vital to understand needs, demand and delivery.

SECTION 3: IMPACT ASSESSMENTS

16. Which groups or communities do you think will be most affected by the transition to net zero, and in what ways?

Many rural areas and island communities already face structural inequalities, including limited access to services, out-migration of young people, and reliance on low-margin agricultural livelihoods. As outlined in our [response to the LUS4 proposals](#), a focus on private finance to deliver public outcomes from climate policy, such as peatland restoration targets, through reliance on expansion of natural capital markets, risks exacerbating these divides if wealth generated through carbon and biodiversity credits benefits mainly those that control large areas of natural resources, large landowners or external investors. The CCP must therefore commit to ensuring that financial and non-financial benefits from climate-driven land use change are retained locally, and that investment does not drive further concentration of landownership or rural depopulation.

[...]

21. Can you think of any further positive or negative impacts, that are not covered in the impact assessments, that may result from the Climate Change Plan?

When considering impacts on rural and island communities special regard should be given to tenants, crofters and new entrants who may lack capacity and face high transaction costs to engage with complex funding schemes, who may have insecure land tenure and will require landowner consent to benefit from natural capital opportunities, and who be outcompeted in a land market driven by private investors.

SECTION 4: STRATEGIC ENVIRONMENTAL ASSESSMENT (SEA)

22. What are your views on the accuracy and scope of the environmental baseline set out in the environmental report? Are you aware of further information that could be used to inform the assessment findings?

The baseline provided looks roughly correct, but it has the usual limitations of all carbon flux datasets, namely high levels of uncertainty. Significant investment in monitoring infrastructure and equipment is required to improve the precision and precision of the dataset, including additional towers and monitoring equipment. Improvements would require upscaling from spot measurements, which links to the (in)accuracy of current peatland maps. Ultimately, if the mapping is wrong then the carbon estimates will be wrong. There are a lot of assumptions in thin data regarding where emissions are coming from, consistency of emissions, peat depth variance etc.

Whilst significant investment could improve the data and baseline, we also recognise that public funds are limited and that marginal improvements should not necessarily be prioritised over action to achieve climate change mitigation on the ground, e.g., through funds for peatland restoration.

23. What in your view are the most significant environmental effects which should be taken into account as the Draft Climate Change Plan is finalised?

Improving the resilience of landscapes, and specifically wetlands such as peatlands to drought should be a key consideration in restoration and management interventions. Drought conditions can cause and amplify conditions that will negatively affect a range of policy priorities such as nature restoration, flood management, reduction of wildfire risks, and preservation of the historic environment. As stated by [RESPECT researchers Barratt, Whitehouse and Bunting](#): "Poor drought management leading to changes in peatland water table levels can significantly affect the ecosystem services they provide. Drought lowers water levels, increasing the oxygen availability in the drained peat and shifting the system from storing to releasing carbon, affecting climate mitigation." It has been [evidenced](#) that the amount of carbon loss through emissions due to even a short-term drought event can be the equivalent of decades of sequestration. Placing sustainable peatland management and restoration activities in the context of drought management is crucial for effective climate change mitigation and climate change adaptation strategies.

24. What are your views on the predicted environmental effects as set out in the environmental report? Please share any other useful sources.

In addition to our response to Q23, we note that the answer to the question whether peatland restoration projects have wide environmental effects depends on project location, design and delivery. For example, impacts of peatland restoration on biodiversity are likely to be positive in the long term, but initial impacts will depend on the baseline, e.g., a very biodiverse system might experience initial biodiversity losses, particularly if methods are invasive such as reprofiling. Positive impacts might be greater if restoration projects fit into the wider landscape/are part of a network of restoration initiatives, and they may also follow

from changes in management practices following restoration (e.g., lower levels of grazing and restrictions on burning). We also recognise that current peatland uses involving extensive grazing practices that may not only support local livelihoods but also unique habitats (e.g., High Nature Value farming/crofting) and that policy must look at options to support such multifunctional landscapes.

We welcome the extensive references to the historic environment in the Strategic Environmental Assessment but would suggest consistency in the use of terminology. As a topic, the historic environment comes under the heading of cultural heritage. Though the historic environment is explicitly and implicitly mentioned in several of the topic and also sectoral assessments it is not done so using consistent terms or definitions throughout the document. We feel this potentially undervalues the contribution, role and importance of the historic environment within several of the nine topics and also more than half of the seven sectors. We would also welcome a qualified mention in the assessment of effects of the positive effects of peatland restoration can have on the buried historic environment. Maintenance of functioning hydrological conditions can support the preservation of the historic environment, which includes paleoenvironmental records, all of which can be used to inform sustainable and resilient intervention and management strategies. It is also important to highlight the potential impact of peatland restoration techniques on the historic environment where intrusive action is planned. This is especially important in the context of a significant aim to accelerate peatland restoration activities that may place pressure on the availability of specialist advisors.

RESPECT [supports a shift towards outcome-based public funding](#), including [Peatland ACTION funding](#), to help ensure broad positive environmental and social effects of peatland restoration. Allocating funds on the basis of clearly defined, transparent outcomes rather than hectare counts will contribute to a more effective targeting of public funds to deliver for multiple policy objectives, e.g., climate change mitigation *and* adaptation, biodiversity, water quality and water management, community wealth building and a just transition, as well as potential benefits from and for the historic environment.

25. What are your views on the proposals for mitigation, enhancement and monitoring of the environmental effects set out in the environmental report?

Proposals for mitigation and enhancement of positive effects relating to policy action on peatlands in the non-technical summary are limited, so we are focusing our comments on the detailed assessment in Annex D. In this regard, we welcome the expanded focus on peatlands to not only include restoration, but also protection of existing peatlands that are already in good condition, preventing further degradation and sustainable (agricultural) management, in order to deliver wide positive effects for climate, biodiversity, soil, water, population and human health, and cultural heritage. Particularly important is the proposal to continue working "with partners and stakeholders to develop incentives, guidance and advice on peatland stewardship within the new agricultural support framework for land-owners and managers looking to enhance peatland protection, management and restoration on their land". However, continuous delays in the development and implementation of a new Scottish agricultural policy and associated financial insecurity for landholders should also be recognised as a key challenge for the protection, sustainable management and restoration of (agricultural) peatlands and the delivery of a wide range of public environmental benefits.

We refer to Q13-15 for a more detailed response to the proposals on peatlands as captured in the CCP.

SECTION 5: MONITORING EMISSIONS REDUCTIONS

The following questions concern the reporting of annual emissions reductions:

26. What are your views on the proposed approach to reporting annual emissions output and how this could support public understanding of Scotland's progress towards achieving our Carbon Budgets?

Hectares of restored peatland is a simple metric that corresponds with Scotland's targets for peatlands. However, whilst we understand why it is being used in absence of sufficient resources to improve peatland and carbon data, we, again, emphasise the limitations of this approach. Potential GHG sequestration varies across hectares and at different points in time, and anticipated future climate mitigation benefits from restoration may not be realised due to the temporal and spatial developments of landscapes, e.g., local heating due to climate change. It must be recognised that we are working under high levels of uncertainty.

Whilst we understand that the focus of this Plan is on climate change mitigation and, therefore, carbon sequestration, a more holistic approach to monitoring peatlands would benefit a more integrated approach to peatland policy overall. E.g., hydrology is relatively easy to monitor and may be of particular importance for the overall functioning of peatland ecosystems, including for climate change adaptation (flooding/drought). We refer to work being undertaken under [Peatland ACTION's Monitoring Strategy 2024-2030](#) (and commitments under the new [Peatland ACTION Five Year Partnership Plan 2025-2030](#) to strengthen the approach to evaluating and monitoring the benefits for climate, nature and people of peatland restoration).

27. How useful do you think reporting emissions statistics at a more detailed level (including at the sub-sectoral level), would be in helping people understand key sources of emissions, and our progress in reducing them?

Reporting emissions at smaller-scales, sub-sectoral level, and at the level of individual environments would be helpful. However, this will require significant investment, and it needs to be clear what such investment will mean for the availability of public funds for actual action such as peatland restoration and creation.

SECTION 6: MONITORING JUST TRANSITION

The following questions concern the 14 proposed indicators for monitoring and evaluation of the Climate Change Plan:

29. Please detail any specific changes that would improve any of the 14 proposed indicators, including any data sources not currently included within this framework that could provide a useful indicator of progress towards a just transition in Scotland on an annual basis.

The initial phase of the legal and policy work under the RESPECT project has focused on identifying barriers to realising a just transition to net zero through the restoration and sustainable management of peatlands. From Annex 3, we understand that the proposed indicators reflect an initial attempt to partially capture what is required for a just transition to net zero in Scotland and that a more comprehensive just transition M&E framework is still in development. We, therefore, focus our response on potential key issues and omissions, but we would welcome an opportunity to contribute to the development of the wider framework.

Representatives of the land use and agricultural sectors emphasised, through [engagement activities with the Just Transition Commission](#), the need to better integrate just transition policies with *land reform* – emphasising that just transition outcomes may be more easily achieved through inclusive land governance. Land reform is, however, largely absent from the CCP and, in our view, the just transition indicators do not do enough to scrutinise the (lack of) inclusivity of decision-making processes for land use change that is required to achieve net-zero targets (e.g., through peatland restoration) at a local level. Our response to Q1 has highlighted a lack of a clear, coherent and well-supported strategic approach to directing land use (change) at policy level, and there is significant reliance on voluntary action (by landowners and landholders) to deliver key public environmental goods including climate change mitigation through land use change. It is at this level of decision-making that a just transition lens requires us to ask critical questions, namely *who* has the power to decide on peatland use and *how* risks and benefits from land use change are distributed, also taking into consideration historical inequalities. Accordingly, just transition indicators should help us to measure progress towards more inclusive processes and more equitable sharing of benefits and risks.

30. What are the most appropriate indicators for judging whether we are achieving meaningful public participation in decisions related to the climate? This includes both the quality of the participatory process itself, and the impact of that participation on the decision-making process.

Indicators of meaningful public participation should go beyond measuring engagement at policy level and instead capture how communities and relevant parties such as tenant farmers or crofters are able to influence decisions at the point where climate action is delivered on the ground. It is at the local level where trade-offs between climate mitigation, biodiversity, food production, access, livelihoods and cultural values are experienced most directly. An increasing focus on (unregulated) markets to deliver land use change – with decisions being primarily shaped by economic opportunities – will also make it increasingly difficult for policy to direct decisions on land and, therefore, participation at policy level becomes less impactful.

Indicators should therefore prioritise participation where decisions are being made, not only where high-level policies are being written. In the context of peatland restoration, this would require monitoring of the number and type/diversity of people involved in peatland restoration projects (e.g., number of crofter/tenant farmer and community-led projects or projects with community representatives on the board in receipt of Peatland ACTION funding or registered under the Peatland Code). It could also involve the monitoring of the content of publicly available Land Management Plans (LMPs) under the new Land Reform (Scotland) Act 2025 and the number of plans that consider peatland restoration and the sustainable management of peatlands, as LMPs require largescale landowners to set out how they intend to manage the land in a way that contributes towards achieving the net-zero emissions target, and plans must be prepared through community engagement.

31. What indicator would provide the best measure of the impact of net zero development in local communities across Scotland? For example, the impact of the installation of renewable energy infrastructure or other land use changes (e.g. through peatland restoration or tree planting).

The current indicator will monitor the “proportion of people reporting that changes to their local place due to net zero infrastructure and/or land use change have maintained or improved the quality of their local area” relying on new survey questions in the Scottish Climate Survey to gather the necessary data, including impacts of land use change on sense of place and local identity. We consider this to be a positive indicator to be included.

In addition, an indicator should be included to capture views on community benefits that have been delivered through land use change including peatland restoration, with (monetary and non-monetary) community benefits to be understood in a broad sense in accordance with [guidance from the Scottish Land Commission](#). These can, for example, include local employment (Q 32), local procurement and investment opportunities, as well as local environmental benefits such as reduced flood or wildfire risk, improved water quality, enhanced biodiversity and/or improved access to greenspace.

32. Ensuring positive outcomes for workers who have transitioned from jobs within high-carbon industries is central to delivering a just transition. What specific data or indicators could we use to monitor the extent to which workers in high-carbon industries are securing alternative employment?

Currently, the indicators reflect a focus on the oil and gas and renewable energy sectors when assessing opportunities for green jobs. We reference the focus of [Peatland ACTION's new Five-Year Partnership Plan 2025-2030](#) on training and expansion of the workforce to support a just transition through restoration. Highlighting the many challenges for green job creation through the peatland restoration industry as outlined under Q 2, it will be important both for the delivery of the Peatland ACTION Five-Year Plan and the CCP to monitor job creation through peatland restoration, particularly at the local level and including “[young and early-career professionals](#)”.

33. What specific data or indicators could we use to meaningfully monitor the impact of the transition to net zero on the environment and biodiversity across Scotland on an annual basis?

“Hectares of peatland restored per year” is listed as a proposed just transition indicator, similarly to the proposed indicator for peatlands in the draft LAJTP. The CCP recognises that the indicator does not reflect the socioeconomic implications of peatland restoration and should be read together with indicators 1.1 and

1.4. However, we believe that even when read in conjunction (and noting the focus of the participation indicator on policymaking rather than direct participation in land use decisions) the area-based indicator risks obscuring crucial details about the quality of restoration, the delivery of multiple benefits including climate and biodiversity (Q 24), and the social impacts of carbon and hectare-focused restoration at a local level. In particular, Scotland has a heavily concentrated pattern of land ownership and decision-making power over land. Area-based targets risk prioritising restoration at scale – see the new Peatland ACTION Five-Year Plan which invites “larger projects to increase scale, efficiency and value for money” – instead of directing support to build capacity and overcome transaction costs for more complex projects. Such projects may involve parties that have faced barriers when accessing public and private finance including communities, crofters, tenant farmers, small-scale landowners, grazing committees etc. Better indicators and measures of success are needed to ensure that peatland restoration delivers fair outcomes, not simply physical outputs. Indicators should be embedded at the local level and capture whether restoration supports community wealth building, local livelihoods and

meaningful participation, rather than reinforce persisting inequalities. In this context, we do not consider “hectares of peatland restored per year” to be an appropriate measure of a just transition.

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